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Research Article

PUBLIC AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION TOWARDS BARIATRIC SURGERY AMONG COMMUNITY IN SAUDI ARABIA

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Abstract

Background: High prevalence of obesity was reported in Saudi Arabia since decades. Bariatric surgery is considered as the most common effective and permanent method for treatment of obesity and decreasing the long-term mortality and morbidity worldwide. In addition, bariatric surgery is one of the most common elective gastrointestinal procedure done nowadays.

Objectives: To evaluate the level of awareness and attitude towards bariatric surgery among Saudis.

Methods: A questionnaire based on cross-sectional study self-administrator was distributed among 450 Saudi participants between the periods November 2018- December 2018. The questionnaire was based on 3 aspects including subject's demographics, perception about obesity and knowledge about Bariatric surgery.

Results: Overweight and obesity were found to be high among Saudi population. The most common causes for obesity were bad life style habits and genetic factors. There was a good knowledge about obesity but moderate knowledge about bariatric surgery as majority of participants believe that lack of physical activities is a risk factor for obesity (63.8%) and Majority of participants chose that bad life style habits could cause obesity (71.1%).

Conclusion: The knowledge of participants regarding the obesity and its risk factors were high but the knowledge about Bariatric surgeries were low-moderate. These results indicated that efficient public awareness campaigns about obesity and Bariatric surgeries are needed to fill the gap and to increase the level of awareness toward obesity and its complications.

Keywords: Obesity, awareness, perception, Bariatric Surgery, KSA, Saudi Arabia

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INTRODUCTION:

KSA was reported high incidence and prevalence of obesity with about 33% of Saudis are obese and more than 50% are overweight [1]. There are many factors contribute to high incidence and prevalence of obesity including some diseases such as T2DM, metabolic syndrome and hypertension. Also, life style such as diet and exercise play a significant role in obesity [2].

Obesity has essential role in many morbidities and mortality and contribute in many diseases such as metabolic and cardiovascular diseases [3]. Obesity is a preventable and treatable disease that could be managed by life style modification like doing regular exercise, eating healthy food [4]. Surgical intervention of obesity has shown a great benefit for reduction of weight and decreasing the rates of obesity complications [5].

Bariatric surgery is considered as the most common, effective and permanent method for treatment of obesity and decreasing the long-term complications [6]. The aim of this study was to evaluate the level of awareness and knowledge towards bariatric surgery among Saudi population.

METHODS:

Cross-sectional study was conducted among Saudi population from November 2018- December 2018 in KSA with a sample size of 450 participants. exclusion criteria; Non-Saudi participants, age less than 18 years old and incomplete data. Consent was obtained from all participants included in the study. The questionnaire included 3 items:

- 1- Demographics such as age, gender and education.
- 2- Perception about obesity.
- 3- Knowledge about bariatric surgery.

Statistical analysis

Data were entered into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and analyzed.

RESULTS:**Socio-Demographic Characteristics**

Table 1 showed the demographic characteristics. The majority of the participants were males (55.5%) while female were (44.4%). The age of the Most of the participants were more than 30 years (64.5%). Most of participants have college degree (47%), 36.5% have primary and secondary degree and 16.5% were illiterate.

Table (1): Demographic Characteristics (n=450)

Male	250	55.5
Female	200	44.4
18-30	160	35.5
More than 30	290	64.5
College	211	47
Primary- Secondary	164	36.5
Illiterate	75	16.5

Perception about obesity:

The awareness of participants toward obesity showed that roughly half of the participants consider obesity is a disease and the other half don't consider the obesity as a disease with (44.7%) and (42.2%) respectively. The majority of participants believe that lack of physical activities is a risk factor for obesity (63.8%) while only (16.9%) don't believe that if there is relation between physical activities and

obesity. More than half of the participants believe that hereditary factors could result in obesity while (30%) don't believe that if there is relation between hereditary and obesity. Majority of participants chose that bad life style habits could cause obesity (71.1%) while (18.5%) don't know if bad habits could cause or not. Most of the participants believe that obese people may develop diabetes and hypertension as complications (82.9%).

Table (2): perception about obesity

	No	Yes	Don't Know
Q1: Obesity is a disease?	190(42.2%)	201 (44.7%)	59(13.1%)
Q2: Lack of physical activity is a risk factor for obesity?	76(16.9%)	287(63.8%)	87(19.3%)
Q3: Hereditary factors contribute to obesity?	132(29.3%)	243 (54%)	75 (16.7%)
Q4: Bad life style habits could result in obesity?	47(10.4%)	320(71.1%)	83(18.5%)
Q5: Obese subjects are vulnerable to diabetes and hypertension?	41(9.1%)	373(82.9%)	36(8%)

Knowledge about Bariatric surgery:

Regarding public knowledge toward bariatric surgery, the result shows the majority of participants don't believe that the only way for getting rid of obesity is surgery (63.8%) while (29.3%) of participants believe that the only way to rid of obesity is surgery. More than half of the participants don't

know if there are complications could result of loss weight surgeries (55.6%) while the rest agree and disagree with this statement (23.1%) and (2.3%) respectively. Majority of participants believe that weight loss surgery decreases the mortality rate (57.8%) while quarter of participants don't know if it decreases the mortality or not.

Table (3): Knowledge about Bariatric surgery

	No	Yes	Don't Know
Q1: Is surgery the only way for getting rid of Obesity?	287(63.8%)	132 (29.3%)	31(6.9%)
Q3: is there complications could result from weight loss surgeries?	96(21.3%)	104(23.1%)	250(55.6%)
Q4: Does weight loss surgery decrease the mortality rates?	72(16%)	260(57.8%)	118 (26.2%)

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

This study aimed to evaluate the level of awareness toward bariatric surgery and it shows there is an acceptable level of awareness among Saudis community and could be due to high percentage of obesity in Saudi Arabia. Many studies have shown a high prevalence of overweight and obesity among Saudi population [7].

The most common causes for obesity were bad life style habits and genetic factors which was consistent with other studies showing that lack of exercise and eating fast foods were a major factor contributing to obesity [8].

The results showed that there was a good knowledge about obesity but moderate awareness about bariatric surgery.

In conclusion, the knowledge of participants about obesity and its complications were high but the perceptions about Bariatric surgeries were low-moderate. These results indicated that efficient campaigns about obesity and Bariatric surgeries are needed for control of obesity and its complications.

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